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BIOTECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CAGE GROWING OF AFRICAN CATFISH IN THE CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

On May 15, 1260 kg of fish stock (70 g) were planted in fish cages installed in the Tuyabuguz reservoir (Uzbekistan) African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*, I grew until mid-October. They fed minced meat made from the insides of broiler chickens. By mid-October, the average individual body weight reached 1300 g, the total biomass - 23400 kg. The total increase in fish biomass for 5 months amounted to 21740 kg. Kormovoy's coefficient in the experiment turned out to be 3.2. The fish productivity of cages was about 25 kg/m³.

Keywords: Aquaculture, fish cages, African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*, fish feeding, Uzbekistan.

Introduction

With a very limited list of warm-water species - objects of fish farming for temperate climate conditions, further expansion of the list of cultivated species can be largely due to tropical fish. No, such fish cannot overwinter in our geographical conditions. IX cultivation in open conditions is of interest when the growing season is fully used when the water temperature of surface water bodies warms up sufficiently (above 18 °C). This period lasts from April to mid-October (more than 5 months) [2, 412]. Under the conditions of intense use of water resources in the republic with the current level of technological effectiveness of the agricultural sector, another aspect of increasing fish production is the adaptive system of keeping fish to the existing diverse types of water bodies, primarily lentic ones. Prospect is the cultivation of tropical fish in cages installed in reservoirs, is. the development of real technologies for integrated water use. Floating fish cages of the valley to be

resistant to local conditions, incl. to strong waves even with single strong wind events per year. During the rainy season, only African nutmeg catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*), grown until now mainly in closed conditions with heated water, which increases its cost [4, 52]. The purpose of this work was to conduct and monitor the experimental and demonstration cultivation of commercial African catfish in the conditions of the Tuyabuguz reservoir in the Tashkent region (the Angren river basin).

Material and Method

2019 in the garden institution of the fish farm LLC "Fish Berg" in the western part of the Tuyabuguz water intake (Fig. 1.). In the process of growing, the main hydrochemical indicators of the fishery quality of water in cages in the surface layer (0.5-1 m on a club) were determined.

Fig. 1. Cage farm of LLC "Fish Berg" in the western part of the Tuyabuguz reservoir.

Material and construction of the basket. The design of octagonal floating cages was developed independently in 2018, the frame is made of a 4 * 4 mm square profile with a thickness of 1.7 mm. The volume of one stand is 300 m³ (diameter 13 m). Buoyancy is maintained by plastic barrels with a volume of 200 liters. The cages were installed near the dam at a gap 500 meters from the shore, at the place where the water depth was set to 30 m; a boat was used to service the cages.

Fish stock. The cages were stocked with African catfish stock (30-100 g) with an average individual weight of 70 grams. The fish seed material was purchased in the hatcheries of the Tashkent region, where the larvae are obtained under conditions of controlled temperature on an industrial scale in January, the juveniles are grown in the pools by May to the indicated sizes, which makes the development of cage culture of this object promising.

In the middle of May, we stocked 3 cages, each with a density of 22 fish/m³. During the growing season, two fish were sorted by size, sorting all the fish into two groups (small, and large).

Feeding. Catfish are fed with a mixture of minced meat from the insides of broiler chickens. At the same time, in the first 15 days, fishmeal (60: 40, respectively) and premix were added to the entrails of the chickens (daily 1 kg in the total amount of the feed mixture). Then only minced meat was prepared from the entrails of the chickens with the addition of 1 kg of the premix part. Taking into account that it was soft and fried, the fish freely tore off and swallowed.

Upon reaching 500 grams of fish, the sample is cut with unprocessed special giblets, and after reaching 1000 grams with chicken feet, heads and beetles are saturated.

The entrails of broiler chickens (offal, heads, legs, minced meat, and bones) were purchased daily at the slaughterhouse of poultry farms in the Pskent district of the Tashkent region.

The diet (wet food by weight) for juvenile catfish with an average weight of 70 grams was 13% of the fish biomass, with the growth of the fish, the diet was reduced to 2% for commercial fish weighing 1 kg or more. Diet corrector according to control hives and water temperature. For this reason, a 10-day control is carried out and a general method is used to calculate the average individual body weight of an African.

Fishing of cages was carried out in mid-October.

Results

As our experience in the operation of fish-breeding floating cages in the conditions of a sharply continental climate of the republic has shown, the storm resistance of feeding lavish cages increases when several cages are connected and a single system is used for such a system, a permanent cable of 20 mm is used. It should be noted that we installed the cage system in a place with a depth of up to 30 m. To withstand waves in strong winds, anchors weighing over 400 kg were used. For construction, the anchor is a plastic 200-liter barrel with a hole and a 3-4-meter pipe with a metal pipe, and a concrete barrel with filling. The anchors were attached to the cage system with the power of a nylon

rope. The length of the rope depends on the depth of the reservoir.

Temperature regime. During the entire period of growing marketable fish, the temperature of the water in the cage itself and the fumigation space was the same. On the experimental side of water intake from May 1 to June 1, the average water temperature rises from 17° C to 24° C. During June and until the end of August, the average daily water temperature in the reservoir warmed up to a maximum of 29° C. In September, the water temperature is from 25° C to 15° C, and the water temperature is 15° C.

Thus, the water temperature in the garden, established in the Tuyabuguz reservoir during the period from May to October, is warm enough for the life and growth of the African catfish.

The pH values varied from 7.0-8.3, which is acceptable from a fishery point of view. It should be noted that the hydrochemical indicators of fish of commercial water quality were also favorable for the African catfish.

Biotechnology of growing marketable fish. The fish stock was delivered on 15 May in 25-liter plastic drums, and each drum contained 15 kg of fish biomass. Before releasing the fish, the temperature of the water in the tank (24° C.) and the garden (20° C.) was balanced.

The total biomass of fish stock was 1260 kg, and the average weight of an individual was 70 g.

Feeding began the next day after stocking. The ratio was 13%. In the evening and at night, a 150-watt light bulb was hung over the cage to attract plankton organisms, followed by small weedy fish that freely entered the cage. At night, we visually constantly noted the catfish hunting for these small fish.

The average water temperature in June was 25° C. According to the data of the control bed, the average individual body weight reaches 160 g, and the total fish biomass in the nursery is 3000 kg. The ration was set at the level of 13% of the horse's biomass, the amount of compound feed and compound feed was about 400 kg per day.

The average daily water temperature in July increased to 29° C. The catfish grew and reached an average of 380 g. The total fish biomass in the cage line increased to 7000 kg. Due to the growth of catfish, the diet was reduced to 8.5% of the biomass. The average daily amount of feed brought in this month reached 600 kg per day.

The average water temperature in August was 27° C. The average individual weight of fish reaches 820 g, and the total biomass – is 14500 kg. Diet size 4.1%, average feed intake 600 kg per day.

The average daily water temperature in August was 27° C. The average individual body weight of fish reached 820 g, the total biomass - 14500 kg. The ration was reduced to 4.1%, the average daily feed intake was 600 kg per day during this period.

The average water temperature in October is up to 22° C. Long-term growth of fish, the average individual body weight reaches 1300 g, and the total biomass increases to 23400 kg. And the cost of products is affordable and affordable.

During the entire cultivation of commercial African catfish, 71,000 kg of feed were introduced into all cages. The total increase in fish biomass for 5 months amounted to 21740 kg. The feed coefficient in the experiment was 3.2. The fish productivity of cages was about 25 kg/m³.

Conclusion

The Tuyabuguz reservoir is located in the flat part of the Akhangaran river basin in the Tashkent region. It can be assumed that the temperature regime of water corresponds to the rest of the lentic reservoirs of the flat part of the rivers of Uzbekistan. In the reservoir, the water temperature regime is favorable for growing tropical (and warm-water) fish for about 5 months. With regard to such fast-growing fish as the African catfish, it can be considered that the period is sufficient for the production of marketable fish, provided that the feeding cages are stocked with high-quality fish stock. In our case, when stocking the cages in May with an average sample size of 70 g, the African catfish grew to 1.5 kg in mid-October.

Cultivation of African catfish in fish-breeding floating cages in reservoirs and lakes of the flat part of Uzbekistan is promising and will allow to produce significant additional fish products [3, 214; 1, 270]. The functioning of the cages does not require any correction in the mode of operation of the reservoirs. Fish live in water, but they themselves do not spend it, and do not change its quality, i.e., fish cages do not interfere with the functioning of the water bodies of the country's irrigation system.

However, growing fish in fish cages should be classified as aquaculture in open conditions, i.e., subject to seasonality. The practice of recent years shows that in the second half of autumn, all producers of African catfish in open conditions carry out total fishing and bring products for sale. As a result, there is a glut of the market in a short period of the year, the price of African catfish falls. The rest of the year, the African catfish is not present on the market. Considering the above, it is possible to recommend the development of catfish fish processing technologies, for which it would be advisable to produce a one-time large number of high-quality products. This will drastically increase the prospects for replication of cage rearing of African catfish in cages.

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